

A Statistical Approach to the Strength of Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials containing more than one type of fibers in a common matrix are known as hybrid composites. In the existing strength theories of hybrid composites, it is often assumed that fibers of the same type all have the same failure strain. In the actual fiber composites, however, the strengths of fibers are not uniform and, therefore, a statistical approach becomes necessary to predict more precisely the behavior of hybrid composites.

This paper first presents analysis of the state of local stress redistribution at a fiber breakage. The results are then incorporated into a Monte Carlo simulation to model the strength and failure behavior of hybrid composites. In the case of glass/carbon hybrid, it has been demonstrated that the GFRP phase plays the role of a crack arrester due to its high elongation capacity. Some comments on the "hybrid effect" are also shown in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials containing two or more types of fibers in a common matrix have become well known as hybrid composites. Hybrid composites have several advantages compared with conventional composites. For example, the freedom of tailoring composite properties increases; the material cost can be reduced by using less amount of expensive fibers such as carbon or boron; and fracture toughness or crack arresting properties can be improved.

The strength of a conventional composite is often predicted by the rule of mixtures. The same idea can be applied to hybrid composites[1,2]. Figure 1 shows an example of a CFRP/GFRP hybrid composite, where V_f is the fiber volume fraction, the superscripts c and g denote carbon and glass fibers, respectively, and the total fiber volume fraction ($V_f = V_f^c + V_f^g$) is taken to be constant. The stresses at points A, D, B, and E are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{A: } \sigma_{\text{GFRP}} &= \sigma_f^g V_f + \sigma_m' (1 - V_f) & \text{D: } \sigma_{\text{CFRP}} &= \sigma_f^c V_f + \sigma_m'' (1 - V_f) \\
 \text{B: } K \times \sigma_{\text{GFRP}} & & \text{E: } \sigma_m' (1 - V_f) &
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where σ_m' and σ_m'' denote, respectively, the stresses of the matrix at the failure

Fig.1. Strength of hybrid composites

Fig.2 Hybrid model for stress concentration factor

strains of glass and carbon fibers, and K is the ratio of failure strains of carbon fiber to glass fiber. Relation similar to Eq.(1) can be written for combinations of any two kinds of fibers. In the following, discussions are limited to the combination of low elongation (LE) fibers and high elongation (HE) fibers.

The rule of mixtures type relation of Eq.(1) assumes that all LE fibers have a unique failure strain, and so are the HE fibers. In the actual fiber composites, however, the strengths (or failure strains) of fibers are not unique. Even if a small amount of fibers is broken, the hybrid itself will not fail. Multiple failures of LE fibers often observed in hybrid composites indicate that fibers have some scattering in strength. Thus a statistical approach becomes necessary to predict more precisely the strength of hybrid composites.

A Monte Carlo simulation is used here to examine the strength or failure strain of hybrid composites. The model for the Monte Carlo simulation treats the unidirectional fiber composite as a series of bundles of chains as proposed by Rosen[3]. To conduct this simulation, it is necessary to know the state of local stress redistribution at a fiber breakage. In the case of hybrid composites, the problem of stress redistribution has been examined by Zweben[4], Chou and Fuluda [5] and Fukuda and Chou[6,7] for the case of static stress concentration and Ji, Hsiao and Chou[8] for dynamic stress concentration. This paper first describes the stress concentration factors (SCF) and next the detail of Monte Carlo simulation is shown.

Hayashi[9] is believed to be the first to observe that the failure strain and hence, the strength of LE fibers appear to be greater in the hybrid than in the all LE fiber composite. He named this phenomenon a "hybrid effect." Bunsell and Harris[10] attributed this effect to residual compressive thermal strains in the LE fiber. Thermal stress contribution is now widely agreed although this is not sufficient to explain the whole of the hybrid effect. Zweben[4] tried to explain the non-thermal part of the hybrid effect from a statistical calculation. His calculation was, however, not for the enhancement

of the initial failure strain but for the enhancement of the ultimate failure strain. More recently Manders and Bader reported experimental observations[1] and statistical explanation[11] of the hybrid effect.

This paper treats the particular form of "hybrid effect" arising from the enhancement of the ultimate strain in the hybrid as compared to that in the LE fiber composite.

STRESS CONCENTRATIONS

There are two types of hybrid composites: interlaminated (or interply) and intermingled (or intraply) hybrid composites. This paper primarily deals with an ideal intermingled hybrid composite sheet of thickness h , which is shown in Fig.2. The LE and HE fibers assume alternating positions at a space d . The fibers in Fig.2 can be regarded as either mono-filaments, fiber bundles or laminae because the governing equations are the same for these cases. A pair of LE and HE fibers are grouped together and labelled by m . For the purpose of numerical calculation, only a finite number of fibers are considered. Figure 3b demonstrates the case of a five-fiber model with 3 LE fibers and 2 HE fibers. All fibers outside of this region of modeling are assumed continuous (cf. Fig.3a). Each fiber in the region can be either continuous or discontinuous. Let R be the ratio of extensional rigidity of the HE and LE fibers; both conventional ($R=1$) and hybrid ($R \neq 1$) composites are considered. $R=1/3$ is assumed in the present calculation for simulating the case of a glass/carbon hybrid composite.

Fig.3. Five-fiber model for Monte Carlo simulation

The governing equation and the solution procedure of the stress concentration problem based upon the shear-lag analysis have been given in Refs.[6] and [7]. Thus only the numerical results of a general fiber breakage model are presented in Tables 1 and 2 for conventional and hybrid composites, respectively. The fiber breakage pattern considers all the combinations of 1, 2, 3 and 4 fiber fractures in a transverse plane. The symbol x in the tables indicates the fracture of the fiber. For instance, for pattern No.1 of Table 1, an LE fiber in the $m=0$ group is broken and the stress concentration factor (SCF) for the nearest fiber is 1.333 which is consistent with Hedgepeth's result[12] for a single broken fiber. Similarly, the SCF of the fiber nearest to two fiber fracture (No.6 of Table 1) is 1.6 which is again the same as the Hedgepeth's result.

It is natural to consider that some fibers outside of five-fiber region will also fail during the actual failure process. The SCF in the region will also be affected by the failure of outside fibers. Therefore, the present calculation tend to give smaller SCF in the region than that in the actual composite, because all fibers outside of this five-fiber region are assumed here to be continuous. Thus, the suitability of a 5-fiber model for the prediction of composite strength behavior is difficult to assess precisely. However, Zweben [13] has shown for conventional composites that failure will occur at a stress level at which multiple fiber fracture takes place. The work of Fukuda and Kawata[14] also suggests that unstable fracture of conventional composite can occur due to the breakage of a few adjacent fibers. The model adopted by Oh[15] for the Monte Carlo simulation of conventional composites also used five fibers. It is thus expected that the basic failure characteristics of a hybrid composite can be grasped by using a 5-fiber model.

MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

Since the procedure of Monte Carlo simulation adopted here is similar to that of Refs.[5] and [14], only a brief summary is shown here. Figure 3b shows

a model for Monte Carlo simulation. Each fiber is composed of N links of length 2δ , where δ is known as the "ineffective length[3]." As the initial condition, a stochastic strength, STR(i,j), is assigned to each link, (i,j). A normal distribution for the strength of links has been adopted.

Stress concentration factors of all links, SCF(i,j), are initially assigned as 1. A link with the least value of STR(i,j)/SCF(i,j) is sought, and let this link be (i₀,j₀). When this link breaks, stress concentrations take place in the links of i=i₀. Then SCF(i₀,j) is replaced by the corresponding values given in Tables 1 and 2 for conventional and hybrid composite; respectively. Then a link with the smallest value of STR(i,j)/SCF(i,j) is again sought among MN-1 links; this link breaks second. This procedure is repeated until all links in a same plane transverse to the loading direction are broken.

Table 1. SCF of conventional composites

pattern	m=0		m=1		m=2
	LE	HE	LE	HE	LE
1	x	1.333	1.067	1.029	1.016
2	1.333	x	1.333	1.067	1.029
3	1.067	1.333	x	1.333	1.067
4	1.029	1.067	1.333	x	1.333
5	1.016	1.029	1.067	1.333	x
6	x	x	1.600	1.143	1.067
7	x	1.802	x	1.419	1.105
8	x	1.412	1.412	x	1.359
9	x	1.368	1.156	1.368	x
10	1.600	x	x	1.600	1.143
11	1.419	x	1.802	x	1.419
12	1.359	x	1.412	1.412	x
13	1.143	1.600	x	x	1.600
14	1.105	1.419	x	1.802	x
15	1.067	1.143	1.600	x	1.219
16	x	x	x	1.829	1.219
17	x	x	2.022	x	1.454
18	x	x	1.755	1.537	x
19	x	2.022	x	x	1.647
20	x	1.778	x	1.778	x
21	x	1.557	1.755	x	x
22	1.829	x	x	x	1.829
23	1.647	x	x	2.022	x
24	1.454	x	1.022	x	x
25	1.219	1.829	x	x	x
26	x	x	x	x	2.032
27	x	x	x	2.286	x
28	x	x	2.359	x	x
29	x	2.286	x	x	x
30	2.052	x	x	x	x

It is not so easy to evaluate accurately the strain of a model with partial fiber breakage. It is assumed that the strain of each link is constant throughout the length, 2δ , and it is proportional to the SCF of the link by linear elasticity. The average value of the strains of all links is regarded as the average strain of the model.

In the following, the results of the simulation for a model of five fibers (M=5) and 20 links (N=20) in a fiber are presented.

Figure 4a shows a typical sequence of link failure of a composite with one type of fiber, where the strength of link follows a normal distribution with an average normalized strength of 1 and a standard deviation of 0.1. The arabic numbers in Fig.4 show the sequence of fracture of links and 0 indicates that the link is not broken. In this model, the link of i=14, j=2 broke first; the link of i=5, j=4 broke second; finally, the failure occurred at the transverse plane of i=14.

Table 2. SCF of hybrid composites

pattern	m=0		m=1		m=2
	LE	HE	LE	HE	LE
1	x	1.777	1.121	1.060	1.031
2	1.131	x	1.131	1.030	1.010
3	1.121	1.777	x	1.777	1.121
4	1.010	1.030	1.131	x	1.131
5	1.031	1.060	1.121	1.777	x
6	x	x	1.412	1.135	1.059
7	x	2.768	x	1.952	1.172
8	x	1.817	1.261	x	1.170
9	x	1.864	1.250	1.864	x
10	1.412	x	x	2.038	1.173
11	1.146	x	1.270	x	1.146
12	1.170	x	1.261	1.817	x
13	1.173	2.038	x	x	1.412
14	1.172	1.952	x	2.768	x
15	1.059	1.135	1.412	x	x
16	x	x	x	2.511	1.291
17	x	x	1.570	x	1.209
18	x	x	1.559	1.965	x
19	x	3.106	x	x	1.496
20	x	2.999	x	2.999	x
21	x	1.965	1.559	x	x
22	1.522	x	x	x	1.522
23	1.496	x	x	3.106	x
24	1.209	x	1.570	x	x
25	1.291	2.511	x	x	x
26	x	x	x	x	1.741
27	x	x	x	3.725	x
28	x	x	1.904	x	x
29	x	3.725	x	x	x
30	1.741	x	x	x	x

Fig.6. Cumulative distribution of the strength of conventional and hybrid composites

conventional and hybrid composites. The stress σ and strain ϵ of composites are normalized by the average strength (σ_{LINK}) and average failure strain (ϵ_{LINK}) of the links of LE fibers. Since a fiber is a chain of N links, the average strength (hence the average failure strain) of fibers is smaller than the average strength of links. According to the present simulation, the initial failure strains of LE fiber composite and hybrid composite are nearly the same. However, their behavior after the initial fiber failure is significantly different from each other. The LE fiber composite fails in a brittle manner whereas the stress-strain curve of the hybrid resembles that of an elastic-plastic metallic material.

The cumulative strength distribution of conventional and hybrid composites are shown in Fig.6. This figure indicates that the strength of hybrid composite is lower than that of all LE composite. This will be reasonable because the HE fibers do not reach their ultimate strength at the failure strain of LE fibers.

Figure 7 shows the cumulative ultimate strain distributions of both conventional and hybrid composites. In contrast with Fig.6, the failure strain of hybrid is larger than that of LE fiber composite. The enhancement of the ultimate strain reaches approximately 50%, and it demonstrates a hybrid effect. It can be concluded from these results that an advantage of hybrid composites lies in the enhanced strain to failure by sacrificing some amount of strength and stiffness.

Manders and Bader[1] postulated that the hybrid effect may be defined as being any observations where the first failure stress lies above BCD or the ultimate stress above ACD of Fig.1. We will check now where the present results locate in Fig.1. The following values are assumed to calculate Eqs.(1): $\sigma_f^g = 2\text{GPa}$; $\sigma_f^c = 2\text{GPa}$; $V_f = 0.5$, $\sigma_m' = 80\text{MPa}$; $\sigma_m'' = 30\text{MPa}$; and $K=1/3$. If the diameters of carbon fiber (or bundle) and glass fiber (or bundle) are equal, $V_f^c/(V_f^c+V_f^g)$ becomes 0.5 from the present model of Fig.2. Then the average values and the standard deviations of the strength of the hybrid, GFRP, and CFRP are as shown in Fig.1.

It may be strange that the strengths of GFRP and CFRP of the present calculation do not coincide with the rule of mixtures (points A and D of Fig.1, respectively). In the rule of mixtures, the average strength of fibers has been taken to be the average of each individual fiber. It is well known that the

Fig.7.
Cumulative distribu-
tion of failure strain

Fig.8
Stress-strain curves of
bonded and unbonded
specimens of inter-
laminated hybrids

strength of a bundle of fibers is smaller than that of individual fiber. The above result shows this effect. The present data for the strength of hybrid, on the other hand, lie above the BD line of Fig.1. Thus the hybrid effect in the sense defined by Manders and Bader is also achieved.

INTERLAMINATED HYBRIDS

Bunsell and Harris[10] conducted a series of experiments and especially paid attention to the effect of bonding between carbon and glass laminae in an interlaminated hybrid. One significant difference between bonded and unbonded specimens is that the load drop of unbonded specimens at the failure of carbon layers is drastic; whereas the failure of the hybrid in the bonded specimens occurs gradually. A simulation corresponding to the above experiment is also possible, although the SCF in a laminated hybrid must be calculated again from the beginning and small modification of the model for simulation is necessary. Figure 9 shows results of the stress-strain curves of bonded and unbonded models. The model considered here is a two-layer hybrid, CFRP/GFRP, whereas Bunsell and

Harris used either four-layer (GFRP/CFRP/CFRP/GFRP) or three-layer (GFRP/CFRP/GFRP) laminated plates. However, the primary behavior can be grasped by a two-layer model. Although quantitative comparison is difficult for the lack of information, the general features of the stress-strain curves of Fig.9 are quite similar to those of experimental curves[10].

SUMMARY

This paper first evaluates the stress concentration factors in conventional and hybrid composites. Based upon the knowledge of stress redistribution at fiber breakages, the strength of hybrid composites is predicted by means of Monte Carlo simulation. The stress-strain relation of a hybrid is different from those of the component fiber composites. The failure of hybrids progresses gradually; its ultimate failure strain is higher than that of the LE fiber composite and a hybrid effect is realized. The present technique of analysis for the intermingled hybrid has been applied to an interlaminated hybrid composite, although the description is rather short. The difference of stress-strain curves between bonded and unbonded specimens is demonstrated; the results coincide with the experimental observations by Bunsell and Harris.

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